

SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE AND AWARENESS OF THE PALESTINIAN ISSUE AMONG ISLAMIC YOUTH IN TURKEY

Rana Fathi Abu-Hassan

Media Department at the Islamic University of Gaza, Palestine

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17453337>

Abstract

This study investigates the extent to which Muslim youth residing in Turkey rely on social networks to follow the Palestinian issue, the motives behind their engagement, and the resulting cognitive, emotional, and behavioral effects. Adopting a descriptive survey methodology, data were collected electronically from 142 respondents studying in Turkey using a structured questionnaire. Findings indicate that respondents' confidence in information obtained from social media about the Palestinian issue was moderate, averaging 67.6%. The primary motive for following the issue was its significance, with 63.0% of respondents highlighting its importance. Cognitive effects were most pronounced in raising awareness of threats to Al-Aqsa Mosque, averaging 74.8%, while emotional effects reflected growing concern for the fate of the Palestinian issue (65.2%). Behavioral effects, particularly engaging in discussions and forming opinions about the events, were reported at 67.4%. The study underscores the role of social networks as a vital source of information and engagement for Muslim youth on geopolitical issues, shaping their awareness, emotions, and civic discourse regarding Palestine.

Keywords: *Social Networks, Palestinian Issue, Youth, Islamic World, Civic Engagement*

Introduction

1. METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

The Palestinian issue is considered to be the most important issues that disturbs the Islamic world, as the Israeli occupation authorities continue to impose their control on most of the Palestinian territories, tightly besiege the Gaza Strip, and systematically attack Jerusalem and Al-Aqsa Mosque, which has made the Palestinian-Israeli conflict the focus of attention of the world in general, and the young Muslims in particular regardless of their origin countries.

The Turkish Republic has always been giving way to Muslim students from all over the world to study in its universities. Hence, the idea of this study was to identify the extent to which the young students of the Muslim world studying in Turkey depend on social networks- as one of the media that comes to the forefront of the youth concerns in following up the Palestinian issue and identifying the most important cognitive, emotional and behavioral effects resulting from this dependence.

1.1. First: The Previous Studies

- Ali Bukhatem's Study (2018): The study concluded that Facebook represents an important news asset, especially in light of social and political change; due to its availability, ease of use, and low cost, as it also gives its users the opportunity to express opinion freely and communicate with the existing connectors, and offer an immediate resonance¹.
- Mohsen Saleh's study (2016): The study concluded that the developments witnessed by the "ring states" - especially Syria and Egypt - and the effects of the crises therein may turn into a major threat to the Palestinian issue at the present stage; since the process of reshaping the region involves reshaping the axes, based on a new definition of priorities and alliances, and assessing the sources of threat, suggesting that the Arab-Israeli conflict is no longer the central conflict in the region².
- Ibrahim Al-Masri's study (2016): The study concluded that 5% of the sample of the study use social networking sites to market the Palestinian issue, while 14.5% of the respondents indicated that they do not use social networking sites in marketing the Palestinian issue³.
- Mohammed Al-Suweid's Study (2015): The study concluded that the prevalence of Twitter use among Saudi university youth is a predominant feature. The intensity of youth use of Twitter focused on follow-up, read-only, forward, and Twitter, followed by a lesser degree: reply, comment, and participation in the (hashtag⁴.
- Shadan Abu Yaqoob's Study (2015): The study found that social networking sites contributed to enhancing political and social awareness among of An-Najah National University students, strengthening political values and political participation, and educating the public on events related to the Palestinian issue⁵.
- Aaron Smith (2014): The study found that social media is not limited to political activity but addresses other aspects of community life, and that there is no separation in online and offline political participation⁶.
- Abdul Sadiq Hassan Study (2013): The study concluded that Bahraini university students prefer YouTube, Facebook and Twitter mainly. The main use of these sites is for friendship. The utilitarian motives for exposure to others' views on community issues were at the forefront of young people's motivation to use newspapers and websites⁷.
- Reem Al-Majali's study (2012): The study concluded that the most important social networks on which Saudi youth rely on as news sources are: Twitter, Facebook, and YouTube, and that the reasons for use are due to that they are easy, fast, and clear in terms of news and developing events⁸.
- TalaatIssa study (2012): The study concluded that Facebook was the most used social media by the respondents to raise awareness of the Palestinian issue, followed by a huge margin, Twitter, then LinkedIn. The respondents' use of these networks is because they allow them to reach different parts of the world and reach the widest possible audience⁹.

- The Guthie Neil Amalar study (2011) found that respondents use Facebook more than Twitter because they consider it as a small blog, and 12% of the public use the Internet once a week, and 19% use it 2-3 days a week¹⁰.

- 11-TahaNajm and Anwar Al-Rawas (2011): The study found that internal political issues dominated the focus of students of Sultan Qaboos University, followed by global, then regional political issues. The lack of political information among young people is an important factor in the follow-up of websites, and that these sites satisfy the desires and political needs of the respondents, as well as the websites role in the political socialization¹¹.

1.2. Second: Problem of the Study

It is to identify the extent to which the young people of the Muslim world residing in Turkey rely on social networks to follow up the Palestinian issue, by knowing the most important pages in which they follow the Palestinian issue, the most important topics they follow, the motives behind following them, how they interact with them, and the most important effects for their dependence on them.

1.3. Third: The Importance of the Study

The importance of the study stems from the importance of the issue it addresses, namely: the Palestinian issue, as well as the target audience of the field of study, namely: the youth of the Muslim world studying in Turkey, and the multiplicity of their origin countries. The importance of the study also from the importance of the means being studied: social networks, which studies confirmed their the wide use, especially by young people.

1.4. Fourth: Objectives and Questions of the Study

This study aims at identifying the extent of which the youth of the Islamic world living in Turkey depend on social networks to follow-up the Palestinian issue, by answering the following questions ☐ What is the extent of the respondents' interaction with the Palestinian issue on social networks?

- What are the most important pages through which respondents follow the news on the Palestinian issue on social networks?
- What are the motives of the respondents to follow up the Palestinian issue on social networks?
- What are the topics related to the Palestinian issue on social networks, and that attract the respondents' attention?
- What are the actions taken by the respondents when they read publications on the Palestinian issue on social media?
- What are the effects (cognitive, emotional and behavioral) resulting from the reliance on social networks in the following up the Palestinian issue?

Fifth: Theoretical Framework of the Study

2. MEDIA DEPENDENCY THEORY

Due to the complexity of life in modern societies, and the continuous advancement of media technology, the importance of the media in disseminating information is growing. Davler and Rokeach sat a model to

illustrate the relationship between the media and other social forces, known as Media Dependence Theory¹.

The media Dependency Theory states that the ability of the means of communication to achieve greater cognitive, emotional and behavioral impact, will increase when they perform the functions of information dissemination in a distinctively intensive way¹. The more the means play an important role in the lives of people, the greater the impact is, and the role becomes more important and central, thus the relationship arises between The intensity of dependence and the degree of influence of the medium on people, and the more complex societies become, the greater the dependence of individuals is on the media¹⁴.

The model is based on other several sub-hypotheses:¹⁵

- The greater the degree of instability in society is, the greater the dependence of individuals on the media intensifies.
- The degree of dependence on the media increases when there are few alternative channels of information. The public's degree of dependence on the media varies due to different personal goals, interests, and individual needs.

2.1. Sixth: Type of Study, Methodology and Tools

This study is to descriptive study that describes a particular subject in reality in terms of the general and detailed characteristics of the subject¹⁶, and used the survey method, which is an organized scientific effort that helps in obtaining data and descriptions of the phenomenon in question¹⁷. Using the survey tool, which is useful in identifying a range of information, opinions and patterns of practice from a large group of respondents¹⁸, to identify the extent to which the youth of the Islamic world rely on social networks to follow up the Palestinian issue

The paper was presented to a group of referees, and the investigation sheet was modified based on their observations¹.

2.2. Seventh: Study Population and Sample

2.2.1. Study Population

The study population consists of students studying in the Republic of Turkey, who are non-Turkish citizenships, but belonging to Islamic countries during the academic year 2018-2019.

2.2.2. Sample of the Respondents

The researcher electronically selected a simple sample of 142 students randomly, who are studying in Turkish universities, and coming from Islamic countries.

2.3. General Personal Characteristics of the Respondents

Table1: shows the distribution of respondents according to general personal characteristics

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	85	59.9
Female	57	40.1
Total	142	100.0

Nationality	Frequency	Percentage
Palestinian	25	17.6
Arabian	83	58.5
Foreigner	34	23.9
Total	142	100.0
Academic Qualifications	Frequency	Percentage
General Secondary School	11	7.7
Bachelor degree	59	41.5
Master degree	46	32.4
Ph.D.	26	18.3
Total	142	100.0
Major	Frequency	Percentage
Humanitarian Studies	87	61.3
Sciences	37	26.1
Islamic Studies	18	12.7
Total	142	100.0

Analyzing the manifested table above, data show as follows:

2.3.1. Gender

Male respondents were 59.9% and females were 40.1%.

2.3.2. Nationality

Respondents from the Arab countries reached 58.5%, foreign nationals were 23.9%, whereas Palestinian citizens along with other nationality respondents reached 17.6%.

2.3.3. Experience

Respondents holding a bachelor degree were 41.5%, those holding a master degree reached 32.4%, and those having a doctorate degree reached 18.3%, and those having high school certificate were 7.7%.

2.3.4. Specialization

The results indicate that 61.3% of the respondents majored in human studies, 26.1% specialized in natural sciences, and 12.7% of the respondents specialized in the Islamic studies.

2.4. Eighth: The Basic Concepts of the Study

- Social networking: These are web sites that allow users to create pages and private spaces within the same site, which allow them to communicate with friends and disseminate contents and communicate fast between different countries and keep information updated¹⁹.
- The Palestinian issue: "A term referring to the historical and political conflict and the humanitarian problem aftermath in Palestine since the first Zionist Congress in 1897 until today. The question of

Palestine is an essential part of the Arab-Israeli conflict that resulted from the emergence of Zionism and Jewish immigration to Palestine. The question of Palestine revolves around the legitimacy of the occupation of the Palestinian land. The issue of refugees, the massacres committed by the occupation against the Palestinians, the operations of resistance against the occupation, and the resolutions issued by the United Nations, the most prominent of which are: Resolution 194 and Resolution 242²⁰.

- Youth: means young adults between the ages of 18-30 years, and have a high school diploma, or those in the process of university study, and affiliated to university to obtain degrees in the stages: bachelor, master and doctorate.
- The Islamic world: a term given to geographical areas and areas inhabited by Muslims, which constitute more than 50% of the total population.

3. RESULTS OF THE FIELD STUDY

This paper reviews the results of a field study conducted on Muslim youth to find out the extent of their dependence on social networks to follow up the Palestinian Issue.

3.1. First: The Extent of Interaction with the Palestinian Issue on Social Networks

This part of the second section discusses the extent of interaction with the Palestinian issue on social networks. It contained the degree of confidence in such information, the means to follow up the Palestinian cause, the language through which they follow up, the most important topics related to the Palestinian issue being followed by the respondents, and the measures taken when the respondents saw a publication on the Palestinian issue.

3.1.1. Following up the News of the Palestinian Issue on Social Networks

Table2: shows the frequency and percentages of respondents' follow-up to news of the Palestinian Issue on social networks

Statement	Frequency	percentage
Yes	87	61.3
No	7	4.9
Sometimes	48	33.8
Total	142	100.0

Based on the Analysis of the Manifested Table Above, Data Show that

The results of the field study indicated that (61.3%) of the Muslim youth follow up the Palestinian issue on social networks, (33.8%) of Muslim youth sometimes follow it up, and (4.9%) do not follow it at all.

The results of the study showed an increase in the percentage of respondents who follow the Palestinian issue through social networks, due to its ease of use, spread and quick access to information related to it. The results of the study are consistent with the findings of the study Bokhatem's study (2018) that Facebook is an important news asset, especially in light of political and social change.

It also comes in agreement with the results of the study (Issa, 012), which found that Facebook was one of the most popular social networks used by the respondents to raise awareness of the Palestinian issue.

3.1.2. The Degree of Confidence in the Information you obtain from Social Networks about the Palestinian Issue

Table3: shows the frequency, percentages, mean, relative weight and standard deviation of the respondents' confidence in the information they obtain from social media networks

Confidence degree	Very low	low	Medium	Large	Very Large	Mean	Relative Weight	Standard Deviation
Frequency	2	8	74	39	12	3.38	67.6	0.790
%	1.5	5.9	54.8	28.9	8.9			

(N= 135)

Based on the Analysis of the Former Table, Data Show that

The relative weight of the degree of confidence in the information obtained by respondents from social networks on the Palestinian issue reached (67.6%), which is a medium degree. The medium confidence ranked first with an average degree of (54.8%), then the large confidence ranked second with an average degree of (28.9%), followed by very large which ranked third with an average of (8.9%). Low degree of confidence ranked fourth with an average of (5.9%), and finally, very low degree of confidence ranked fifth with an average of (1.5%). The researcher believes that the decline of the respondents' confidence in the information on the Palestinian issue may be due to the multiplicity of sources of information, or due to the conflicting information that those sources make about the Palestinian issue, or as a result of the media coverage dedicated to the scenes of the Palestinian political division more than the coverage dedicated to the Palestinian issue itself and the transfer of information from trusted sources.

3.1.3. Following up the News of the Palestinian Issue on Social Networks through Media Pages

Table4: shows the frequency and percentages of respondents' responses on the means of following up the news of the Palestinian cause on social networks

Pages	Frequency	percentage	Rank
International Media	84	62.2	1
Activists in solidarity with the Palestinian issue	74	54.8	2
Palestinian media	72	53.3	3
Local media	49	36.3	4
Palestinian Resistance	43	31.9	5
Turkish media	38	28.1	6
Palestinian Political Figures	31	23.0	7
Other	2	1.5	8

(N= 135)

Data Analysis of the Former Table Shows that The Muslim youth following up the Palestinian issue on social media through international media ranked first with an average of (62.2%)s, followed by "activists in

solidarity with the Palestinian issue" ranked second with an average of (54.8%). Palestinian media ranked third with an average of (53.3%). The Local media ranked fourth with an average of (36.3%), and the Palestinian resistance ranked fifth with an average of (31.9%), whereas following the Turkish media ranked the sixth with an average of (28.1). Finally, following up the Palestinian issue through the Palestinian political figures ranked seventh with an average of (23.0). The researcher attributed the high follow-up of respondents to the international media amount of coverage, thus meeting the results of the study (Saleh, 2016) that the effects of the crises witnessed by the "Arab Ring-Countries" may turn into a major threat to the Palestinian issue at this stage.

The researcher attributed the reasons for the high follow-up to the international media, perhaps due to the fame of the means affiliated to them, and the follow-up of respondents to what solidarity activists publish on the Palestinian cause is due to the coexistence of these solidarity activists to the details of the Palestinian cause, and briefing them on the images of the sufferings of the Palestinian people caused by the Israeli occupation, which contributes to increase awareness of the Palestinian issue as confirmed by the study (Abu Yaqoob, 2015).

3.1.4. The Language in which Muslim Youth Follow up News on the Palestinian Issue Through

Table6: shows the frequency and percentages of the language through which the respondents follow the news of the Palestinian Issue

Language	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Arabic	107	79.3	1
English	73	54.1	2
Turkish	54	40.0	3
Local	19	14.1	4
Other languages (French, Mali)	7	5.2	5

(N= 135)

Data Analysis of the Former Table Shows that

Respondents who follow up the Palestinian issue in Arabic ranked first with an average of (79.3%), followed by English which ranked second with an average of (54.1%), then came the Turkish language in third rank with an average of (40.0%). Local languages ranked fourth with an average of (14.1%). While Other languages such as French and Mali ranked fifth and the last at (5.2%).

The researcher explains the high percentage of respondents who follow the Palestinian issue in Arabic to the fact that they are of Arab origin, and that a high percentage of them follow the news of the Palestinian cause in English may be due to the fact that they come from Islamic countries that speak English, or that the content published by social networks on the Palestinian issue is presented in good part in English. And this comes in consistent with the results of the current study, which pointed to the high proportion of respondents who follow up social networks to the international media.

3.1.5. Most of the Topics that Attract the Attention of the Respondents Regarding the Palestinian Issue

Table7: shows the frequency and percentages of the respondents on the most interesting topics regarding the Palestinian issue

Subjects	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
Zionist violations against the Al - Aqsa Mosque	95	70.4	1
Zionist attacks against Jerusalem and its people	84	62.2	2
The siege of the Gaza Strip and its effects	74	54.8	3
Palestinian Resistance News	71	52.6	4
Jerusalem uprising against the Zionist occupation	56	51.4	5
Turkey's attitudes and policies towards the Palestinian issue	40	29.6	6
My state's attitudes and policies towards the Palestinian cause	40	29.6	7
Palestinian - Israeli negotiations	34	25.2	8
Efforts and movements towards Palestinian reconciliation	17	12.6	9

(N= 135)

Data Analysis of the Former Table Shows that

The Zionist violations against Al-Aqsa Mosque ranked first as they attract the attention of the respondents with an average of (70.4%). Then comes the Zionist attacks against Jerusalem and its people which ranked second with an average of (62.2%). The siege on the Gaza Strip and its consequences ranked third with an average of (54.8%).

News of the Palestinian resistance ranked fourth with an average of (52.6%). News concerning the Jerusalem uprising against the Zionist occupation ranked fifth with an average of (51.4%). The positions of Turkey and its policies towards the Palestinian issue ranked sixth with an average of (29.6%). The issue of "My state's attitudes and policies towards the Palestinian issue" ranked seventh with an average of (29.6%). Whereas the issue of the Palestinian-Israeli negotiations ranked eighth with an average of (25.2%). "Efforts and movements towards the Palestinian reconciliation" ranked ninth with an average of (12.6%).

The results of the study showed an advancement of the issues related to the violations of the Zionist occupation against the Palestinian issue vis-e-vis the decline of the position of Turkey and the respondents' states towards the Palestinian issue compared to those attacks, and this is due to the fact that social networks shed light on the results of the attacks and violations of the occupation of the Palestinian

issue or that the solidarity activists' concern is to reveal these crimes and attacks to raise awareness of the dangers facing the Palestinian cause, and to mobilize international public opinion to support them. This role of social networks came in consistent with the studies conducted by (Boukhatem, 2018), (Abu Yacoub, 2015), (Smith, 2013) and (Issa, 2012).

3.1.6. Action Taken when Muslim Youth See a Publication on the Palestinian Issue

Table8: Action taken when Muslim youth see a publication on the Palestinian cause

Action taken	Frequency	percentage
Do more than one action	41	30.4
Read only	37	27.4
Tell my friends outside the Internet	21	15.6
I like it (like)	16	11.9
Share it with others (share)	16	11.9
I comment on it	4	3.0
Total	135	100.0

(N= 135)

Data Analysis of the Former Table Shows that

In terms of actions taken when Muslim youth see a publication on the Palestinian issue, the first item i.e. "they do more than one action" ranked the highest with an average of (30.4%), "reading only" ranked second with an average of (27.4%), then "tell my friends outside the Internet" ranked third with an average of (15.6%), "liking and sharing with others" ranked fourth with an average of (11.9%), commenting on the news ranked sixth with an average of (3.0%).

THE results showed a decline in the percentage of those who admire the publications on the Palestinian issue, or commentators, in contrast to the high percentage of those who do more than one measure, or who are satisfied with reading. Consequently, the results of the current study are in consistent with the results of the study (Al-Masri, 2016) which found that 5% of the sample of the study use social networking sites to market the Palestinian cause, while 14.5% of the respondents indicated that they do not use social networking sites in marketing the Palestinian issue.

3.1.7. The Belief that Social Networks Represents an Effective Way to Support the Palestinian Issue

Table9: shows the frequency and percentages of respondents on the belief that social networks are an effective way to support the Palestinian issue

Statement	Frequency	percentage
Yes	69	51.1
Sometimes	57	42.2
No	9	6.7
Total	135	100.0

Analysis of the Data of the Previous Table Indicates that

The results of the field study indicated that 51.1% of respondents believe that social networks are to be an effective way to support the Palestinian issue, whereas 42.2% of respondents said that social networks are sometimes an effective way to support the Palestinian issue, while 6.7% of respondents do not believe in that.

The researcher believes that the high percentage of respondents who answered yes and sometimes on their belief that social networks represent an effective way to support the Palestinian cause is due to the various advantages enjoyed by such networks, such as: cosmic, proliferation, mass, and accessibility, as well as the popularity among young people. These results are supported by the results of the aforementioned studies of (Boukhatem, 2018), (Sweden, 2015), (Abu Yacoub, 2015), (Smith, 2014), (Hassan, 2013) and (Almajali, 2012), and Isa, 2012).

3.2. Second: The Effects of the Dependence of the Respondents on Social Networks in Following up the Palestinian Issue

This part of the second section discusses the extent of the respondents' interaction with the Palestinian cause on social networks, It contains the most important cognitive, emotional and behavioral effects resulting from the respondents' dependence on social networks to follow up the Palestinian issue.

3.2.1. The Most Important Cognitive Influences on the Palestinian Issue Resulting from Dependence on Social Networks

Table10: *Frequencies and responses of respondents on the most important cognitive effects resulting from reliance on social networks to follow up the Palestinian cause*

Cognitive Effects	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Awareness of the threats facing Al - Aqsa Mosque	101	74.8	1
Read the news on the siege of Gaza and its implications	81	60.0	2
To know the practices and violations of the Israeli occupation towards Palestinians everywhere	74	54.8	3
Identify the Palestinian resistance struggles	71	52.6	4
Know the latest developments and information on Palestinian issue	63	46.7	5
Know Arab and international positions on the Palestinian issue	53	39.3	6
Know Turkey's positions on the Palestinian issue	34	25.2	7
Identify the Palestinian-Israeli negotiations	32	23.7	8
Know the positions of the state I belong to regarding the Palestinian issue	32	23.7	8

(N= 135)

By Reviewing the Data of Table (10) the Results Indicate that

The most important cognitive effect on the Palestinian issue resulting from the dependence on social networks according to Muslim youth was the awareness of the threats endangering the Al-Aqsa Mosque which ranked first with an average of (74.8%). To read the news of the siege imposed on Gaza and its effects ranked second with an average of (60.0%). To know the practices and violations of the Israeli occupation towards the Palestinians in all places ranked third with an average of (54.8%). To identify the championships of the Palestinian resistance ranked fourth with an average of (52.6%). To know the latest developments and information on the Palestinian issue ranked fifth with an average of (46.7%), and "To know the Arab and international attitudes towards the Palestinian issue" ranked sixth with an average of (39.3%). "To Know Turkey's positions on the Palestinian issue" ranked seventh with an average of 25.2%. "To identify the Palestinian-Israeli negotiations" and "To know the attitudes of the state to which I belong to" both came finally with an average of (23.7%).

The results showed a high percentage of respondents who were talking about the Zionist occupation attacks against the Palestinian people, and the Palestinian resistance championships that come in the context of confronting these attacks, and self-defense, and this is what the occupied peoples do to prove their right of existence and defend their just cause. On the other hand, there was a decrease in the influences of cognitive knowledge that are formed through social networks regarding the Turkish role, as well as Arab attitudes, and the attitudes of the countries to which the respondents belong to. The researcher explains that the focus of social media networks regardless of their media or geographical coverage, or what the solidarity activists are doing is to focus on the media coverage of daily attacks on the Palestinians, or the consequences of actions imposed against them, such as: The siege of the Gaza Strip.

3.2.2. Emotional Effects on the Palestinian Issue Resulting from Social Media Dependence

Table11: shows the frequencies and percentages to know the most important emotional effects on the Palestinian issue resulting from dependence on social networks.

Table11: *Emotional effects on the Palestinian Issue Resulting from Dependence on Social Networks*

Emotional Effects	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Growing concerns about the fate of the Palestinian issue	55	65.2	1
Feeling distressed by the state of division in Palestinian society	71	52.6	2
Deepening the challenge of the Zionist project	66	48.9	3
Growing positive feelings towards the Palestinian people	66	84.9	4
Increased hope that the resistance will inevitably prevail over the Israeli occupation	62	45.9	5

Celebrating and winning the Palestinian resistance	59	43.7	6
Enhancing the spirit of cooperation and solidarity with the Palestinian issue, especially during crises	46	34.1	7

(N= 135)

Data Analysis of Table (11) Shows that

The results of the field study pointed out that the most important emotional effects on the Palestinian issue resulting from the dependence on social networks according to Muslim youth was the growing feelings of anxiety on the fate of the Palestinian issue, in which it ranked first with an average of (65.2%), followed by the element that they feel distressed by the state of division in the Palestinian society which ranked second with an average of (52.6%). The third emotional effect was "deepening the spirit of challenge to the Zionist project" with an average of (48.9%), and the growing positive feelings towards the Palestinian people ranked fourth with an average of (84.9%).

The increase of hope that the resistance will inevitably prevail over the Israeli occupation ranked fifth with an average of (45.9%). Celebrating the Palestinian resistance and its victory ranked sixth with an average of (43.7%). Enhancing the spirit of cooperation and solidarity with the Palestinian issue, especially during crises ranked seventh with an average of (34.1%).

The researcher believes that the high degree of anxiety among the other emotional influences came in line with the high amount of cognitive effects as a result of shedding light on the attacks of the Zionist occupation, nevertheless it showed a moderate percentage of the growing positive feelings with the Palestinian issue, which in turn calls for enhancing and marketing these feelings among the public, In contrast, the results of the study reflected a decline in the percentage of enhancing the spirit of cooperation and solidarity with the Palestinian cause, especially during crises compared to other emotional influences, which requires attention to highlight the daily suffering of Palestinians under the ongoing occupation, despite the diversity of its forms, and the degree of antagonistic effects.

3.2.3. The Behavioral Effects Resulting from Relying on Social Networks to follow up the Palestinian Cause

Table12 shows the frequencies and percentages to know the most important behavioral effects on the Palestinian issue resulting from dependence on social networks.

Table12: Behavioral Impacts on the Palestinian Issue Resulting from Dependence on Social Networks

Behavioral Impact	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Discuss the opinion about the events of the Palestinian cause with others	91	67.4	1
Participation in solidarity activities with the Palestinian people	55	40.7	2

Stand by the Palestinian resistance through tweets and hashtags	54	40.0	3
Mobilize Islamic public support for the Palestinian resistance against the Israeli occupation	46	34.1	4
I report the Palestinian issue on my profile	40	29.6	5
Helping Palestinians, especially in times of crisis	38	28.1	6
Participate in events that support the approach of Palestinian-Israeli negotiations	19	14.1	7

(N= 135)

Data Analysis of Table (12) Shows that

The results of the field study indicated that the most important behavioral effects on the Palestinian issue resulting from the dependence on social networks according to Muslim youth was to discuss opinions on the events concerning the Palestinian issue with others where it ranked first with an average of (67.4%). participating in solidarity activities with the Palestinian people ranked second with an average of (40.7%). Standing by the Palestinian resistance through tweets and hashtags ranked third with an average of (40.4%). In the fourth rank came mobilizing Islamic public support for the Palestinian resistance against the Israeli occupation with an average of (34.1%). Reporting news on the Palestinian issue on the pages of personal respondents ranked fourth with an average of (29.6%). Helping Palestinians, especially in times of crisis ranked sixth with an average of (28.1%). Whereas participating in events that support the Palestinian-Israeli negotiations came finally and ranked seventh with an average of (14.1%).

The results of the study reflected the high percentage of respondents who support discussing opinions on the events of the Palestinian issue with others and participating in solidarity activities with the Palestinian people, and standing by the Palestinian resistance through tweets and hashtags vis-à-vis those who convey the news of the Palestinian issue on one's personal page, and this points to variable pictures of solidarity with the Palestinian issue and marketing it electronically. The results also reflected a decrease in the percentage of respondents participating in events that support the approach of the Palestinian-Israeli negotiations and this indicates that they are not convinced of the feasibility of this road to achieve justice that the Palestinian cause deserves it.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Investing the advantages of social networks in marketing the Palestinian issue.
- Strengthening the media content concerning the Palestinian issue on social networks with reliable sources, and diversifying the elements of revealing facts directed at the audience, in order to support their confidence in such information.
- Focusing on foreign languages in marketing the Palestinian cause through social networks.

- Highlighting the daily suffering of the Palestinian citizens in light of the ongoing crisis of the occupation, even if forms of sufferings and the degree of consequences are varied. Thus contributing to instilling a sense of cooperation and integration with the Palestinian cause.
- Urging the solidarity activists with the Palestinian issue to implement various measures to raise awareness of its fairness and the dangers posed to it.

REFERENCES

- Abayat, L. (2019, June 18). *The Palestinian issue*. Retrieved October 16, 2019, from <https://mawdoo3.com>
- Abdel Aziz, B. (2011). *Methods of media research* (1st ed.). Cairo: Modern Books House.
- Abdel Hamid, M. (1997). *Journalism research* (2nd ed.). Cairo: World of Books.
- Abdel Hamid, M. (2010). *Media theories and trends in influence* (3rd ed.). Cairo: Books World.
- Abu Yaqoub, S. (2015). *The impact of social networking sites on the political awareness of the Palestinian issue among An-Najah National University students* (Master's thesis). An-Najah National University, Nablus.
- Almajali, R. (2012). *The extent of Saudi youth dependence on social networks as news sources: A field study on a sample of undergraduate students* (Master's thesis). Imam Muhammad bin Saud Islamic University, Riyadh.
- Al-Suwaid, M. (2015, n.d.). Saudi youth use of social media website (Twitter) and its impact on their degree of relationship with traditional media: A field study on a sample of public and private university students in Riyadh City. Presented at Conference: Social Media: Applications and Professional Problems, College of Information and Communication, Imam Muhammad bin Saud Islamic University, Riyadh.
- al-Masri, I. (2016). The use of social media by the elite in marketing the Palestinian cause. Paper presented at the Third International Conference: The Palestinian Issue, an Issue and a Right, Tripoli: Jeel Center for Scientific Research.
- Boukhatem, A. (2018). *University youth dependence on Facebook as a source of news: An exploratory study of Jilali University students, Khamis Miliana* (MA Thesis). Jilali University, Algeria.
- Hassan, A.-S. (2013). The exposure of university youth to social networking sites on the Internet and its relationship with traditional means of communication. *GCC Series, 1*. Riyadh: Cultural and World Affairs Sector in the Gulf Cooperation Council.

- Hejab, M. (2010). *Theories of communication* (1st ed.). Cairo: Dar Al Fajr for Publishing and Distribution.
- Issa, T. (2012). The use of social media by Palestinian universities students in awareness of the Palestinian cause: An empirical study. Paper presented at the Sixth Forum of the Saudi Society for Media and Communication: "New Media: Theoretical and Applied Challenges," King Saud University, Riyadh.
- Jothi, M. N., & Shakthi Prasad, R. (2011). Analysis of social networking sites: A study on effective communication strategy in developing brand communication. *Journal of Media and Communication Studies*, 3(7), 234–242.
- Mashaqbeh, B. (2010). *Methods of media research and discourse analysis* (1st ed.). Amman: Osama House for Publishing and Distribution.
- Mekkawi, H., & El-Sayed, L. (1998). *Communication and its contemporary theories* (1st ed.). Cairo: Egyptian Lebanese House.
- Mujahid, A. (2012). Using social networks to provide advanced library services. *Journal of Information Studies, Issue 8*, Monofiya University, Monofiya.
- Najm, T., & al-Rawas, A. (2011). The relationship between Omani youth exposure to new media and the level of political knowledge (Unpublished Master's thesis). Sultan Qaboos University, Oman.
- Saleh, M. (2016). The Palestinian issue and the Arab world in the period 2014–2015 and expected paths. Beirut: Zaytuna Center for Research and Studies.